

The journey towards a conceptual framework... What's the story? Insights from students and parents about the strategies and supports needed to help with a diagnosis of Developmental Co-ordination Disorder in Irish secondary schools.

Abstract

This article contributes to the evidence base on the significance of the journey towards a conceptual framework in research. It draws on research from experts about development of conceptual frameworks. While the area of Special Needs and Inclusive Education is widely researched, little attention has been given to students who are diagnosed with DCD. There is a gap in the literature, in Ireland, from the perspective of how secondary schools can respond to help students with DCD. The conceptual framework charts the map for this research. This article argues that ongoing revisions, as research interacts with stakeholders, change the direction of the journey. The contribution of this conceptual framework is to provide a clear sense of where the research is going. It is hoped that the research will help students with a diagnosis of DCD and their parents gain perspectives on their journeys through Irish secondary schools.

Keywords

Conceptual frameworks; Developmental Co-ordination Disorder; Student Voice

3 Main Highlights

- The importance of the conceptual framework on emergent research in the area of Special Educational Needs (SEN) in an Irish context.
- Development of the conceptual framework.
- Ongoing revisions to the conceptual framework as the research emerges within the context.

Main text

Introduction

In this article, the purpose is to examine the function of a conceptual framework. The readers will be provided with the purpose, rationale and philosophical underpinnings of the research. The evolving framework will be outlined as it has changed, and continues to change, over the course and progress of the research journey. Finally, there will be a presentation of the narrative of the research, including a draft conceptual framework. In this research, examining the issue through the lens of social justice, the proposal is to examine — from the perspective of stakeholders, students and their parents — strategies and supports that will assist students with a diagnosis of Development Co-ordination Disorder (DCD). The students in question are those in secondary school in the Republic of Ireland. The conceptual framework will play a key role in grounding and interpreting the research through the lens of social justice. The conceptual framework must be realistic and flexible as the research progresses in terms of outcomes and results (Kivunja, 2018). A thorough search of the literature will support this development.

Having realistic and measurable outcomes is critical in the area of Special Educational Needs (SEN) research because, in and of itself, the field is so broad and so varied. Numerous studies have defined SEN as a broad area (Jørgensen, Dobson and Perry, 2021; Morley *et al.*, 2021; Nusser, 2021). Most of the research in this area has focused on special needs in general (Weir and McAvinue, 2013; Subasi Singh *et al.*, 2021; Van Mieghem, Struyf and Verschueren, 2022). Little attention has been given to students who are diagnosed with DCD (Kornysheva *et al.*, 2019; Kirk, 2021). There is a gap in the literature, especially in Ireland, and especially from the perspective of how schools can respond to help students with DCD (Blank *et al.*, 2019). While there is a need to understand the nature of the diagnosis and how support

strategies can be put in place at the micro, meso, and macro levels to aid the student (Hepworth Berger, 2008), it is important to point out that this study is not looking at the condition through a deficit lens but, rather, through the model of inclusion. It is hoped that the conceptual framework will keep the study grounded and help explain key concepts to those unfamiliar with the specific language of the research.

In this study, the researcher consults formally with students with a diagnosis of DCD, and their parents, in terms of their lived experience with their diagnosis in school. The research aim is to investigate how students with DCD and their parents feel about secondary school. National online questionnaires will be disseminated to generate quantitative data about lived experiences. Based on these findings, a number of qualitative semi-structured interviews will follow, which will generate an understanding of strategies which could be used to support students with DCD in secondary schools.

The researcher will begin by setting out the research context and the critical role of the conceptual framework. Then, the researcher will outline the methodological approach the researcher hopes to take with the study. While there will always be limitations in research, the slow evolution of the conceptual framework may help to minimise limitations. The framework will play a key role in this regard. However, before the researcher can begin to build on the literature framework, it is important to think about their methodology.

Methodology

The following section will analyse the proposed methodology. The purpose of this explanatory sequential study — which will use mixed-methods research (MMR) — is to capture the voices of students with DCD and the voices of their parents. An explanatory

sequential study was chosen because its post-positivist perspective aligns with the ontological viewpoint of the researcher. First, quantitative data will be generated through online questionnaires issued to parents and students diagnosed with DCD. Some of the respondents (both students and parents) will then engage in qualitative, semi-structured interviews about how they feel concerning strategies that could help them achieve enhanced inclusion in secondary school. A conceptual framework is critical to the emergent themes and topics of research (Leshem and Trafford, 2007; Berman, 2013). It is not simply a roadmap for the journey but, rather, a series of plans which change and evolve over time as the themes and concepts central to the heart of the research become more apparent. The analogy of an exploratory map, which is rudimentary at first but becomes clearer and more advanced as an explorer becomes familiar with the landscape, is somewhat appropriate. However, a conceptual framework serves different purposes throughout the process (Leshem & Trafford, 2007) and the researcher needs to remain cognizant of the fact that outcomes should be realistic and measurable (Kivunja, 2018). It is important to create the framework with an idea of the end in mind. This will serve as an anchor to bring the researcher back to basics at various stages throughout the process; this process depends quite heavily on the literature review.

Literature Review

This section will explore the literature around DCD in Ireland and tie it to the concept of the development of a conceptual framework. A key social justice question underlines the conceptual framework for this research (Van Aswegen, Hyatt and Goodley, 2019; Shafik, 2021). The DES is responding to international and national contexts by creating policies that suggest a move towards inclusion within schools, while meeting the needs of all learners in that environment (Department of Education and Skills, 2016, 2017; McHugh, 2019;

Madigan, 2020). This research will be written against the backdrop of the movement towards inclusion (McHugh, 2019; Inclusion Ireland, 2021). Internationally, the way we view the diagnosis of SEN, such as DCD, has changed, from a medical disability model to a social model (Kanter, 2018; Commission of the European Parliament, 2020; Shafik, 2021). This social model will be the focus of the study. Inclusion is the lens through which the researcher will examine how the Irish education system might put in place strategies and support to assist students with a diagnosis of DCD. The United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (2007) had a major global impact on educational discourse which will influence the context of the study. Article 24 recommended that countries work to allow everyone in society the same educational opportunities, regardless of their special educational needs or otherwise (UNCRPD, Article 24). Alongside this, there has been influence from political forces outside of Ireland — from both the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and the European Commission — driving policy in a certain direction (Kennedy, 2018). The pressure to align our national policy and practice with others is clear (Murphy and Sugrue, 2021). Equity policy is being driven by an international perspective (Rizvi and Lingard, 2009). All of these are key drivers within the conceptual framework. However, there are also professional aspects of the researchers’ experience which may play a key role.

Fig 1: Key policy documents which will inform the development of the conceptual framework

While much has been written about DCD internationally (Edmonds, 2012, 2021; Addy, 2013; Foulder-Hughes and Prior, 2014; Blank *et al.*, 2019; Caçola and Lage, 2019; Barnett. and Prunty, 2021; Kirk, 2021), there is a gap in the literature in terms of an Irish context. The exception is the work of O’Dea, Coote and Robinson (2019), who examined DCD from the perspective of an occupational therapist in an Irish context. Internationally there has been a focus on supporting primary school students who have just had a diagnosis of DCD (Ripley, 2001; Kirby and Drew, 2003; Dixon and Addy, 2004; Kirk, 2021), but very little has been written about the experience of teenagers with DCD (Kirby and Drew, 2003; Addy, 2013). Not only is there a lacuna in the literature in an Irish context, but an online parental forum also notes a lack of clear direction within the system (DCD Ireland, 2017b, 2017a). While there are recommendations made to schools in terms of macro and meso support and strategies(Ripley, 2001; Dixon and Addy, 2004), very little research has been carried out in these areas. This study aims to help bridge the research gap. The establishment of an agreed language in the field is very important with regard to developing a conceptual framework.

Fig 2: Key literature which will inform the development of the conceptual framework

Language is fundamental to the development of critical thinking and theories (Braun and Clarke, 2021). The importance of a shared understanding with a shared vocabulary for key concepts and ideas becomes critical (Forchtner, Jorge and Eder, 2020). Essentially, those writing, reading and critically analysing the concepts must be on the same page thinking about the same ideas (Berman, 2013). This may be even more critical if those reading the research are not as familiar with it as the doctoral candidate (Posselt, 2018). Conceptual frameworks can be used to communicate this shared language (Kumar and Cavallaro, 2018). In this way, the conceptual framework takes on added importance — not only is it the map of the journey for the research, but it also becomes a critical reference point which shares the vocabulary of the discipline (Berman, 2013). In many ways, it may help to bridge the gap between research and the classroom and between policy and practice, which is very much the focus of Hall and Wall's work (2019). In building the shared vocabulary, the conceptual framework helps the researcher create links for those reading the research where everyone is speaking the same language.

Within Irish Education, the Education Act (Government of Ireland, 1998) and the Education for Persons with Special Educational Needs (EPSEN) Act (Government of Ireland, 2004) recognise the importance of education for all students. Irish educational policy has also responded to the influence from Europe, citing both inclusion and equity for all as being at the heart of its focus (Department of Education and Skills, 2019). This movement has directly impacted the students and parents the researcher hopes to interview for this work. There may be a contradiction between what is written in policy and what happens in practice (Ball, 2003; Ball and Junemann, 2011; Ball, 2017; King, 2019; Shafik, 2021). The conceptual framework is the starting point to create this link between policy and practice.

Part of the problem linking policy to practice within the conceptual framework lies in the definition of inclusion. Inclusion has several meanings in our society (Smith and Leonard, 2005; Travers *et al.*, 2010; Banks and McCoy, 2011; Colum, 2020). The definition of inclusion put forward by the National Council for Special Education (NCSE), adopted from the UNCRPD, is most appropriate as it is the one that guides practice in secondary schools in Ireland.

Inclusion involves a process of systemic reform embodying changes and modifications in content, teaching methods, approaches, structures and strategies in education to overcome barriers with a vision to provide all students of the relevant age range with an equitable and participatory learning experience and the environment that best corresponds to their requirements and preferences. (United Nations, 2008)

This is the definition of inclusion that will be used throughout this research, as it is the definition which the NCSE use in their policy advice to secondary schools in terms of how to create positive learning environments for all students (National Council for Special Education, 2019). However, there is not always a clear alignment between the work of the NCSE and the DES.

There is a policy gap within the guiding vision of the DES in terms of where they see the practice of inclusion and the reality on the ground, especially for supporting students with a diagnosis of DCD. On a macro level, there is a sense of the importance of inclusion of all students in secondary education, but the reality is that on a meso and micro level there is very little evidence of this in the procedures needed to apply for support for students with a diagnosis of DCD. There is a vacuum in the policy literature in Ireland directing schools on how to act when a family receives a Special Educational Needs (SEN) diagnosis. Advice is available from the NCSE on how to assess for SEN after a diagnosis has been given (Department of Education and Skills, 2006; National Council for Special Education (NCSE),

(2014a)). However, there is a gap in guidance for secondary schools on the actual suite of support provisions which should be in situ to support the learner to aid full inclusion on the ground in the school (Eagle *et al.*, 2015).

This raises several issues for this research — particularly for choosing those who will participate in the research. First, not all students with a disability will apply for a diagnosis (Kishore *et al.*, 2021; Rosenbaum, Silva and Camden, 2021; Sapiets, Totsika. and Hastings, 2021). While a ‘label’ is no longer required under the new Allocation Model for Schools, how does a school respond to a student who is challenged but has no diagnosis of a disability (Department of Education and Skills, 2017)? How do schools prove that they are meeting all students’ needs whilst also attending to norms of inclusive practice? The reality is that practice in schools may lag behind government initiatives (Van Aswegen, Hyatt and Goodley, 2019; Alves, 2020). How will the conceptual framework address this disjoint? Is this something that will become apparent in the research as it develops?

Secondly, the support model which has been suggested as a route towards inclusion in an Irish context will be relevant within the framework. The concept of the neighbourhood school is the philosophical basis of the model which we see in other jurisdictions — such as India, Portugal and Italy — that have employed a full inclusion model (Narayan, Pratapkumar and Reddy, 2017; Florian and Camedda, 2020; Ianes, Demo and Dell’Anna, 2020; Ramberg and Watkins, 2020; Camedda, 2022). However, there is no overarching governmental policy to support the transition from diagnosis to treatment within the current inclusive framework in Irish schools (Dudley-Marling and Burns, 2014). Once a student has received a diagnosis, they begin a further series of applications for support in school, and then another round of applications for assistance in the State Examinations (Department of Education and Science,

1994; Expert Advisory Group on Certificate Examinations, 2000; Bolt & Thurlow, 2004; DCD Ireland, 2017b; James and Hannah, 2018). The lack of joined-up thinking between the agencies is problematic and leads to inequity (Mitchell, 2018). This evidence suggests that at a policy level, strategies and supports need to be implemented to support communication between everyone involved in supporting a student with DCD, as is the current practice in New Brunswick in Canada (Frizzell, 2022).

Fig 3: Personal and professional practice which will inform the development of the conceptual framework

There is never going to be a perfect education system (Ball, 2018) where every desirable support strategy exists for every single student with an additional diagnosis (Ramberg and Watkins, 2020). The reality is that situations in schools are complex (Dudley-Marling and Burns, 2014) and the conceptual framework must take the key fact into consideration. To begin with, the school may not have the expertise to deal with the diagnosis (Busch *et al.*, 2001; King, 2007, 2019; Cramer, Pellegrini-Lafont and Gonzalez, 2014; Hargreaves. and Fullan, 2015; Teaching Council, 2020). On a macro level, teacher training could be provided from the NCSE, the Post Primary Support Team (PDST), or the Teaching Council (Department of Education & Science (DES), 2005; Teaching Council, 2020; National Council for Special Education (NCSE), (2014a)). In secondary schools, evidence suggests that no one is really sure where they can access training and support (Sugrue, 2009; Gleeson,

Sugrue, and O’Flaherty, 2017). In addition, it could be the case on a meso and micro level in schools that there are insufficient specialist teachers with a knowledge of inclusive practices for all students with a diagnosis, including DCD, available to disseminate inclusive practices to the entire staff of the school. The establishment of a conceptual framework for the research aimed to establish whether or not if these are areas of concern to the participants as will be discussed in the next section.

Designing the conceptual framework

In this section, I will examine how to design the conceptual framework mindful of the philosophical underpinnings of the research. In planning the conceptual framework, the philosophical underpinnings of the research in the area of identifying strategies to support students with DCD became important. Three key paradigms which can inform the research and answer the research hypotheses inform the research: the positivist empirical approach (quantitative); the constructivist approach (qualitative); and the pragmatist approach (mixed methods research — MMR).

To begin with, it is critical to establish the research methodology, which Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2009) call the backbone of the research process. A researcher’s philosophical outlook on life determines the questions they ask about life’s realities and the way they critically evaluate those lived experiences (Gaudet and Robert, 2018; Hattie and Larsen, 2020). Within educational research, it is critical that we are cognizant of our ontological and epistemological assumptions, as we are shaped by the people and situations we have come across (Riddell, 2003; Cavendish and Espinosa, 2013; Qanay, Courtney and Nam, 2021). This is a critical part of research and the design of the conceptual framework.

Pragmatists do not believe in a reality that is objectively and unemotionally observed (Hammersley, 2007). Nor do they believe that they can detach themselves from the world, or the reality of what is in the world (Sefotho, 2015). Socially occurring phenomena are intricate entities (Ochieng, 2009). This is especially true when one is examining the lived realities of other people's lives (Sylvestre *et al.*, 2013; Payne, 2015). There is no single view of any particular educational situation — it can always be viewed through different lenses which highlight different nuances within an issue (Salomon, 1991). Indeed, we need to employ different tools to gain a full and unbiased picture of what is really happening in the world (Salomon, 1991). It is important that the conceptual framework is flexible enough to take account of the nuances and, in turn, produce results that take those nuances into account.

The current study takes note of three paradigms which marry together. The research hopes to capture the overall picture of what is happening within the Irish education system. Then, it will take a closer look at the individual experience. To begin with the questionnaires — following the post-positivist paradigm, there is the acknowledgement of the possibility of biases (Glavin, 2021). These questionnaires will give a balcony view of the current situation. Following on from the broad perspective, the semi-structured interviews, which are qualitative, will allow space for individual voices to be heard. The researcher wants to allow the respondent the freedom to answer honestly (Kvale and Brinkmann, 2009). By incorporating both positivism and post-positivist perspectives, it is hoped that the research will be richer (Jones, 2000). When completing the current study, it will be critical that the researcher is mindful of how their own axiology might influence the research (Panhwar, Ansari and Shah, 2017). The conceptual framework is designed to underpin research which will follow a mixed-methods approach in order to capture a snapshot of what life is like for

an Irish secondary school student with DCD. In any research, it is important to be mindful of ethical considerations.

Ethical considerations

This section will examine a number of ethical considerations to consider in the conceptual framework, including confidentiality and the age of the students taking part (Kvale and Brinkmann, 2009). The conceptual framework, in my research, will focus on both an Irish and international perspective. The research questions and hypotheses formulated in the framework will anchor the research study. Ethical approval will be applied for from Dublin City University (DCU).

Drawing from the existing body of literature exploring learners with a diagnosis of DCD, a questionnaire will be designed from scratch. Experienced researchers in the field will help to guide the development of the questionnaire. It will then be piloted with a small group representative of the larger study group. The questionnaire will be altered as a result of feedback and then circulated to the questionnaire sample digitally. The data generated will be cleaned and analysed using SPSS software. Resultant themes will form the focus of questions for the semi-structured interviews which will be a follow-up from the quantitative part of the study. The same pool of participants will take part. The resultant data will be cleaned and analysed using N-Vivo.

The researcher will produce a thesis that outlines the study and the emergent results. Participant confidentiality will be maintained at all times and the names of the respondents and their schools will not be identified (Creswell and Creswell, 2017). Accurate records of the data will be kept safe, in keeping with the ethical requirements of constructing

trustworthy research and in accordance with data protection requirements in Europe and Ireland (Walford, 2005; DCU, 2020). Students will participate with the permission of and in the presence of their parents. Bearing the ethical considerations in mind, one will now move to discuss the key elements in the construction of the conceptual framework.

Discussion

This section will discuss the key areas of consideration in preparing the conceptual framework to meet the aims of the research. For a research paper into support for SEN in Irish schools, the conceptual framework will suggest three key areas for consideration (Leshem and Trafford, 2007). These three key components are critical to the work of preparing the conceptual framework. To begin, they point to the existence of work in the field that already exists informing practice and thinking. Secondly, they point back to the underlying assumptions of the research as a practitioner in the field, as someone who has had their own critical experiences through their work in the classroom and in schools (Berman, 2013). Finally, there is the interplay between that experience and the ongoing reflection and reading that is part of the journey (Kivunja, 2018). This highlights the importance of reading deeply to identify the subtleties in the research as one is preparing their conceptual framework.

Berman (2013) speaks to the importance of situating the research in the pedagogical environment — a point reinforced by Hall and Wall (2019). However, within this environment, it is important to be mindful of the cultural nuances. These may need to be accounted for in some way in the conceptual framework.

As the research proceeds, the way the researcher views the conceptual framework will change. The conceptual framework may serve as a re-centring tool at different times in the journey (Berman, 2013). The importance of keeping a reflective journal to chart this development is critical in the process of putting together the conceptual framework and also of the entire journey. Leshem and Trafford (2007) point out that a key consideration throughout the work, and in preparation for viva, is the contribution of the work to the overall body of knowledge. The relationship between the changes in the conceptual framework and the reflective journal will chart the journey to the viva and beyond.

The conceptual framework continues to play a critical role throughout the research. It is an anchor that one returns to at various points on the journey, rooting someone to the philosophical assumptions which underline the key themes in the research. Through the literature review, emergent themes will help to focus the questions asked in the online survey (Miles and Huberman, 1994). Through online questionnaires issued to parents and students with a diagnosis of DCD, it is hoped that the researcher will capture a sense of what it is like to live with a diagnosis of DCD. This research should gauge some of the challenges associated with the condition and how these challenges may be addressed with support strategies. Questionnaires will be analysed using SPSS, a software package for statistical analysis (Tolmie, Muijs and McAteer, 2011; Hinton, McMurray and Brownlow, 2014; Pallant, 2020). This software package was chosen for data analysis because of its use in previous educational research and the researcher's familiarity with the package (Hinton, McMurray and Brownlow, 2014). Having analysed the results of the quantitative survey, I will move on to using a qualitative approach to the second part of the research. The questions for the interview will emerge from the themes identified through the questionnaire. Whilst this area of study is of particular fascination and passion to the researcher, one could happily

spend several years researching the Irish context. However, the reality is that the research is limited which one will examine in the next section.

Limitations

This section examines the limitations of the research, which will be taken into consideration when designing the conceptual framework, conducting the research and analysing the results.

Gray (2021) warns that questionnaires often reflect one's own ontological and epistemological views. A researcher needs to be aware of this as it can have a negative influence on the data (Oppenheim, 1992). One of the notable limitations of using self-administered online questionnaires is that the researcher cannot be sure if the respondent understood the questions (Gillham, 2007). Piloting will help to ease these concerns, as it will highlight questions that may cause confusion. In addition, piloting will help to ease concerns about time (Fowler, 2008). It is important that the questionnaire is long enough to generate useful data but short enough that respondents will fill it in to the end (Brown and McNamara, 2021). Good piloting and awareness about the type of questions asked should help limit difficulties (Maxwell, 2021).

Due to time constraints and the nature of the assignment, the sample size for this part of the research will be relatively small (Lee and Lings, 2008). Only students with DCD will participate. Other studies have focused on students with a diagnosis and a possible diagnosis (Kaplan *et al.*, 1998; Miyahara *et al.*, 2017). As a secondary school teacher, the researcher is not qualified to assume a diagnosis and students will therefore need to be formally diagnosed to participate.

The conceptual framework, and later the research, aims to examine the views of Irish students with DCD and their parents; this will, in itself, limit the study. For the quantitative study, a larger cohort will be examined, and it is hoped that there will be a good geographical spread throughout the Republic of Ireland (Swift and Piff, 2014). Distribution of the online questionnaire will occur through social media channels, direct contact with DCD organisations, and through various media outlets (Gillham, 2007; Baker and Foy, 2008). This study is limited because it only looks at secondary school students diagnosed with DCD. Other constraints will include word count, topic, research brief, research tools, etc.

Conclusion

In this article, the area of conceptual frameworks was discussed establishing within a research context the need to develop a conceptual framework. The article yielded a number of important considerations which may help inform practice for others embarking on the journey to creating their own conceptual framework. The importance of the literature review and the methodological approach support the construction of the conceptual framework was underlined. The importance of the conceptual framework as the guide map for the study is highlighted as the metaphor of an anchor which will change and develop as the research evolves. Future research may further explore the iterations of the conceptual framework from the infancy of the study to its completion. It may be of benefit to examine the evolving conceptual framework together with a reflective journey to highlight the critical nature of the conceptual framework at various stages in the journey of the research.

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